

The process of collapse and re-forming the wave function when
measuring the speed of light cannot be ignored, exploring
superluminal motion under the viewing angle principle

Li Yan (李岩)

Abstract: One does not consider the process of collapse and re-formation of the wave function when measuring the speed of light; if this process is considered and a new wave function is formed when measuring the speed of light, the laws of physics will be covariant in all reference frame. The mass-energy increment of the particles due to their relative motion is independent of the formation of the fundamental forces, under the influence of which the speed of the relative motion of the particles will no longer be capped at the speed of light. Macroscopic objects moving with relative speeds exceeding the speed of light will achieve overall quantum tunnelling. In the future, human beings can achieve high FTL motion and become an interstellar civilization.

Keywords: problems in measuring the speed of light, phenomenon of FTL motion.

Author: Li Yan (ORCID ID:0009-0007-9009-140X)

Preface: In my two previous articles, based on relative space and relative space action, I proposed the nature of motion, kinetic energy, gravity, antigravitational model, potential energy, and found a breakthrough to the laws of conservation of momentum and conservation of energy by antigravitational action, and proposed the quantum gravity equation and a unified description of the four basic forces through the viewing angle principle. But there has always been a question about the speed of light. Recently after thought experiment finally found the answer about the speed of light and now present it to you.

1. The process of collapse and re-forming the wave function when measuring the speed of light cannot be ignored

It is well known that Einstein formulated the special theory of relativity in 1905, one of the basic principles of which is the principle of constancy of light velocity: in all inertial systems, the speed of light in the vacuum is equal to c , independently of the motion of the light source ^[1]. The principle of invariance of the speed of light was confirmed by the Michelson–Morley experiment. But can the principle of invariance of the speed of light be **directly applied** to all reference systems?

We know that in quantum mechanics there are effects such as the uncertainty principle, quantum decoherence ^[2], wave function collapse ^[3], and quantum entanglement ^[4]. Since photons are light quanta, all the effects of quanta are applicable in the measurement of photons. Quantum effects cannot be avoided in the measurement of the speed of light.

In the principle of constancy of light velocity, that it is the same speed with respect to all inertial systems. This conclusion is true in any inertial system. But in all methods of measuring the speed of light there is a unique and never-to-be-excluded doubt:

In the process of measuring the speed of light there must be the following situation: while the observer is measuring the photon, the photon's original wavefunction collapses and a new wavefunction is formed, and the photon follows the observer's frame of reference and no longer follows the original frame of reference.

That is, when an observer measures "a photon in another reference system" by any means. the photon wave function simultaneously collapses and generates a new wave function, which is no longer the original speed of light. --Arbitrary means include gravity, and the new wave function

generated by the photon follows the gravity local frame of reference.

So: during the measurement of the speed of light there must be a photon "wave function collapse and re-formation process".

This process can be ignored when measuring the speed of light in a reference system moving at relatively low speeds; we cannot ignore this process when measuring the speed of light in a reference system moving at relatively high speeds.

Corollary: Measuring the speed of light between different reference systems must consider the photon's "process of wave function collapse and re-formation".

(A) When this process is not ignored, the photon forms a new wave function and the laws of physics will covariance in all reference systems.

(B) If the process is ignored, special relativity must be introduced for the laws of physics to covariance in all reference systems.

Although the latter is capable of being correct in most cases with the introduction of Special relativity, and can also derive most of the correct conclusions, the former is more in line with the objective facts when the two are compared with each other.

Simpler and more realistic physical conclusions can be reached when thinking about physical theories without ignoring the "process of wave function collapse and reformulation". For example, in my article "New viewpoint in Physics" ^[5], I described the principle of motion and kinetic energy, in which, when comparing the kinetic energy of two particles in motion with each other, it is necessary to transformation the electromagnetic wave in one of the particles into the relative space of the other particle. The transformation of the relative space is the "process of wave function collapse and re-formation". In this process, it is necessary to consider the speed and direction of motion in the relative space, and it is not possible to simply consider photons/electromagnetic waves as particles that are emitted instantaneously without being affected by motion, and this process is the basic principle of the transformation of electromagnetic waves between relative spaces.

In addition, the basis of the viewing angle principle that I adopted in the Unified Description of the Four Fundamental Forces ^[6] is also since "the process of collapse and re-formation of the wave function" cannot be ignored. According to the viewing angle principle, there is no need to transformation between relative spaces during the formation of the fundamental forces, it follows the principle of constancy of light velocity. Under the viewing angle principle, the "mass-energy increment" caused by the relative motion of particles has nothing to do with the formation of the fundamental force, and even if the particles move at the speeds close to the speed of light, the speed of light, or the speed of superluminal light, it will not change the basis for the existence of the fundamental force, and the magnitude and the direction of the fundamental force will not be changed due to the relative motion, therefore, in the quantum gravity equations proposed by my article must be calculated in terms of static mass.

Since the "mass-energy increment" caused by the relative motion of particles has nothing to do with the formation of the fundamental force, under the influence of the fundamental force, the speed of the relative motion of particles will no longer be capped at the speed of light, and the speed of the object can exceed the speed of light under special circumstances.

2. Means of achieving motion with exceed the speed of light

In my first article, motion with exceed the speed of light was described as follows: particle A is one of the particle models of dark matter. Such a particle, while moving in the vertical line of its

plane without being affected by inertia, can exceed the speed of light due to the repulsive action with a star, provided that the spatial action of that star already exists in the space through which the particle passes. On the other hand, the existence of repulsive action between such a particle and other particles, and the greater the repulsive force the closer the particle is, makes it difficult for it to collide with other particles even if it is travelling at a very high speed, and it can even pass through dense solids with ease [5].

Ways to achieve motion with exceed the speed of light: people can make flying saucers according to the anti-gravity model, use flying saucers as vehicles, obtain larger anti-gravity with higher energy, and achieve continuous propulsion by adjusting the inclination angle of the flying saucers to obtain the anti-gravity of different stars such as the Earth, the Sun, and the Milky Way Galaxy, etc., which can achieve motion with exceed the speed of light.

The various propulsion methods currently implemented by mankind on Earth (including the way in which particles are propelled by high-energy particle colliders) are all flawed, and none of them can enable ordinary particles to achieve motion with exceed the speed of light.

3. Exploring the phenomenon of motion with exceed the speed of light

(1) The collision of a particle motion with exceed the speed of light with an electromagnetic wave/photon does not produce superluminal-shock-wave, an electromagnetic wave colliding with a particle immediately becomes part of the particle and excites a new electromagnetic wave. This is different from the collision of a supersonic object with air molecules, which have mass, whereas electromagnetic waves/photons have no static mass.

The various propulsion methods currently implemented by mankind on Earth (including the way in which particles are propelled by high-energy particle colliders) are all flawed, and none of them can enable ordinary particles to achieve motion with exceed the speed of light.

(2) The process of photon wave function collapse and re-formation when moving at relatively low speeds

First, let's look at the situation at relatively low speeds: according to the phenomenon of aberration of light discovered by Bradley from 1725 to 1728, when an object and a light source are in relative motion, the light received by the object will be deflected in the direction. The angle of deflection is small at low relative velocities, and gradually increases as the relative velocity increases.

When the "wave function collapse and re-forming processes" of photons is not ignored, analyze the cause of the phenomenon: The particle N is at the position N0 when it receives the head of the photon, and while the particle N continues to move forward, the tail of the photon continues to propagate towards the particle N. When the tail of the photon propagates to the particle N, the particle N arrives at N1. Currently, the speed of light is unchanged, the direction of light is the synthesis of the speed of motion and the speed of light (the above analysis is the same as the actual measurement results). As in Fig. 3.1.

Fig. 3.1: Light travelling difference when a moving object receives light

The figure above shows aberration when observing a star (receiving light), and the moving object sees the image of the light source as a virtual image.

According to the principle of aberration above, when a light source emits light, there will also be optical aberration, but the aberration of the emitted light will be different from the result of observing a star.

In considering the photon "wave function collapse and re-formation process", the particle M in the position M_0 when the vertical direction of the emission of a photon, when the head of the photon leaves the M, M continues to move forward, when the tail of the photon leaves the M, the particle M has been moving to M_1 , at this time, the speed of light is unchanged, and the direction of the photon is a synthesis of the speed of motion and the speed of light, as in Fig. 3.2:

Fig. 3.2 The aberration of light of photons emitted by the moving light source

Relative to the system consisting of particle M and particle N, at both the emitting and receiving ends of the photon will undergo the process of photon "wave function collapse and re-formation". As in Fig. 3.2.1:

Fig. 3.2.1 The aberration of light of photons emitted by the moving light source

(3) Phenomena occurring for particles moving faster than the speed of light

When the relative motion of two particles exceeds the speed of light: as in Fig. 3.3, particle M is moving to the right with speed v relative to particle N. When particle M is at M_0 , a photon is

emitted from each of the points a, b, c, d, and e. At the same time, the particle M is in motion, and the photons emitted from the points will appear to be stretched or compressed in the direction of the motion of M.

When the photon is measured at c'', the particle M has moved to M1. The photon measured at c'', the propagation speed is unchanged, still c, but the direction of the photon appears to change: the head of the photon is issued from point c, the tail is biased in the direction of the particle M movement, the direction of the photon is c'→c''. The photon's inverse extension will be intersected by the particle center of mass of the front, the measurements at all other points are the same.

In the direction of propagation shown in Figure 3.3, the most important thing to pay attention to is the photon emitted at point e. Now when the head of the photon is emitted from point e, the particle M has been moving in the direction of the propagation of the photon, and the speed of movement $v > c$. When the head of the photon propagates to the point e'', the tail of the photon leaves the point e'', and thus the direction of the propagation of the photon is changed in the direction of e'→e.

Fig. 3.3 The aberration of light of photons emitted by Superluminal moving particle

When the particle M is moving much faster than the speed of light, the photon propagates as in Fig. 3.4.

Fig. 3.4 The aberration of light of photons emitted by Superluminal moving particle

To sum up, when particle M is moving with superluminal speed relative to particle N, the electromagnetic wave of particle M needs to be transformed from the "relative space of particle M" to the "relative space of particle N", as shown in Fig. 3.5, all the energy of particle M tends to move away from N and is opposite to the motion direction of particle M. The energy of particle M tends to move away from N and is opposite to the motion direction of particle M. opposite to the motion direction of particle M. When particle M and particle N collide, the force is no longer pushing each other, but pulling each other, and the direction of the transferred energy is opposite to the direction of motion. At the same time of the contact, particle M and particle N will present each other with

quantum state, particle oscillation occurs, and the two particles traverse each other's position, without collision. This is analyzed by "relative space transformation".

Analyzed again by the principle of viewing angle: In the perspective of the particle (object) to be collided, all the energy of the superluminal motion particle (object) is directed away from the collided particle (object). In the viewpoint of the superluminal motion particle (object), all the energy of the particle (object) about to be collided with is also directed away from the FTL particle (object). At the moment of contact there will be tunneling effect, and the two objects will pass through each other--even if they collide with a planet.

Quantum tunnelling at speeds below the speed of light has a certain probability, so that only some of the particles in a clump of matter will experience quantum tunnelling, not all of the clump. In the case of superluminal motion, the quantum tunnelling effect will no longer be probabilistic, but inevitable, and the macroscopic object moving at superluminal will achieve quantum tunnelling in its entirety.

Comparing Figures 3.3 and 3.4, the energy of objects moving at superluminal instead decreases as their speed increases, and the less antigravity is required for acceleration.

In the future, when humans on Earth develop to a higher stage, high superluminal motion--thousand times the speed of light, million times, or billion times the speed of light--can be achieved. But to develop to such a stage, human minds need to be dramatically upgraded and equipped with better converging beliefs in the Creator. Humans are currently struggling to get out of their own way on their own planet, let alone enter interstellar space and face the complexity of alien civilizations. In the process of future development, human beings need to think deeply about the meaning of life, kindly treat different beings and even their own creation of intelligence and life, need to think deeply about the fundamental reasons and causes of the existence of the universe, human beings should not draw a picture of the future as a certain kind of impossibility.

The gravitational and anti-gravitational forces on objects moving at FTL are unchanged, as are the electromagnetic, strong, and weak forces, and there is no danger of disintegration into energy. High superluminal motion would transcend the effects of black holes.

Superluminal motion would not turn back time and would not violate the law of cause and effect. It might be easier to discover the existence of the soul and easier to realize the true nature of the self. But if one does evil, the evil effect will manifest more quickly.

4. The operation of electrons outside the nucleus and chemical bonding can be deduced from an in-depth exploration of the strong force model.

According to the description of the strong force in the Unified Description of the Four Fundamental Forces [6], the operation of electrons outside the nucleus and chemical bonding

essentially belong to the same principle as the formation of the strong force. As shown in the diagram, both are maximized by the action of the viewing angle to make the formation of bonding between electrons (chemical bonding) and between protons (strong force).

At the same time, the schematic is also a sketch of the spindle and petal orbitals of electrons outside the nucleus, and the principle of viewing angle also leads to the way electrons combine outside the nucleus, leading to the Pauli exclusion principle and Hund's rules.

The diagram below:

CONCLUSION: Physics and Chemistry form unified rules under the viewing angle principle. The viewing angle principle belongs to the underlying principle.

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